
Educational Administration, Enhanced Functional Education as Correlates of Sustainable Security in Tertiary Institutions in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between educational administration, enhanced functional education, and sustainable security in tertiary institutions in Niger state, Nigeria. A correlational survey research design was adopted, the population of the study comprise all the administrators, lecturers and students of all tertiary institutions in Niger state. A sample of 555 respondents (administrators, lecturers and students) were selected for the study using simple random sampling technique. Two sets of instruments tagged “Administrators and Enhanced Education Questionnaire (AEEQ) and Sustainable National Security Questionnaire (SNSQ) were used for the study. The instruments were validated by 2 experts in the field of educational management, test and measurement who ensured the face and content validity of the instruments. The reliability coefficients of 0.78 were obtained for the AEEQ and 0.85 for SSQ which were high enough for the study. The data were analysed using inferential statistics and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between educational administration and sustainable national security; there was significant relationship between enhanced functional education and sustainable national security. The study recommends that policymakers and educators prioritize the development of effective educational administration systems that can facilitate the implementation of enhanced functional education programmes, thereby promoting sustainable security in tertiary institutions in Niger state, among others.

Keywords: educational administration, enhanced functional education, tertiary institution, sustainable national security

Introduction

Security of lives and properties a primary duty of any leader either politically, socially or culturally. Joshua, Ibietan, & Azuh, (2016) defined security as a condition or feeling of safety from harm or danger. It also means the defense and protection of values acquired. They went further to explain that security has to do with freedom from danger or threat to a nation ability to protect

and develop itself, promote its cherished values, legitimate interests and enhance the wellbeing of its people. The definition overlooked prevention from attack as being an important aspect of security.

Audu and Mohammed (2014) conceived security as any mechanism devised to alleviate the most serious threats that prevent people from pursuing their cherished values. Also, Akin (2008) conceived security as the situation that exists as a result of the establishment of measures for the protection of persons, information and property against hostile persons, influences and actions. It is the existence of conditions within which people in a society can go about their normal daily activities without any threats to their lives or properties. Abubakar (2011) asserted that security embraces all measures designed to protect and safeguard the citizenry and the resources of individuals, groups, businesses and the nation against sabotage or violent occurrence.

Sustainable security refers to the measures taken to protect individuals from harm, violence, or unauthorized access within a nation or territory (Olofinniyi & Adekunle, 2024). It involves creating a safe and secure environment, preventing incidents, and responding to emergencies within an institution.

A safe school environment is critical to education. However, various studies in recent years have shown that the schools are not so safe for the students and for the school personnel any more due to some problems threatening school security. Anya (2008), receiving attention to the responsibility of institution for providing a safe environment so that students and lecturers maximize the education experience, states that institutions are faced with numerous issues involving safety. From preparing for natural disasters to preventing school violence, prevention of student kidnapping and protecting students from illnesses, school administrators are seen responsible for ensuring that students are safe at schools. All these and many more are prevalent in Niger state which constitute serious setback to sustainable security.

Insecurity is unquestionably the most widely spread, indeed broad-based phenomenon that prevails in all parts of the country most especially in the northern part of Nigeria, only comparable to hunger, poverty and hardship (Mkpa, 2020). It remains one challenge that seems to have a defied solution such that the international communities that tried to assist Nigeria in its solution could not make an impressive head way. There is no gainsaying the fact that Nigeria is currently facing serious security challenges, that have put every citizen on the edge including those at the helm of affairs and even the security operatives saddled with the responsibility of securing lives and properties (Omoroge, 2021). Hardly can fellow countrymen and women sleep with their two eyes closed. Since the last four years, there has been a dramatic twist on the wave, dynamics and sophistication of insecurity in Nigeria. Insecurity that used to be one of the lowest concerns in the hierarchy of Nigeria's social problems has now assumed an alarming proportion. A time we thought that corruption and power failure have

the crown of our problems, insecurity in the country has now taken the centre stage.

Insecurity in Nigerian schools and institutions of learning results from external incursion by terrorists, kidnappers and bandits thereby leaving management, parents and guardians helpless. With the existing gap in the security architecture, intervention by security forces and agencies has been weak to detect, deter and destroy threats.

Insecurity is not new to Nigeria. However, it becomes more alarming due to its reoccurrence within the education system in the recent time. Insecurity in schools that affects safety of life and property spread across all parts of the country such that it raises question on the primary responsibility of government. This is happening against the background of low school enrolment across the tertiary institutions in the state and widespread illiteracy in addition to the need to develop the education sector. This may perhaps hinder the sustainable security in tertiary institutions in Niger state.

In securing lives and property of every nation, education is an essential tool. Sadiq (2013) asserts that an educated population is an asset to a nation due to the fact that education promotes national security as it inculcates desirable human traits like honesty, sincerity, hard work, punctuality, productivity, innovation, patriotism, selflessness, brotherhood, friendship, etc. It also empowers people by inculcating life-long skills and know-how thereby liberating the individual from poverty and want. Jonathan (2016) stresses the relationship between education, poverty and security, as he pointed that top ten most literate nations in the world are at peace, while almost all of the top 10 least literate nations in the world are in a state of either outright war or general insecurity. Lower education levels are linked to poverty and poverty is one of the chief causative factors of crime whether it is terrorism or militancy or felonies. To Jonathan, counter insurgency strategies are short term tools for securing a nation from insecurity while education provides a long term solution. Malala (2016) submits that eradicating global terrorism goes beyond proliferation and development of guns and drones, rather spreading quality education across the globe irrespective of regions and culture because “through wars and weapons we can only kill terrorists - but this ideology of terrorism can only be ended through education”, hence, swapping of textbooks and other educational materials for drones and guns (Malala cited in Jayalakshmi, 2014). Malala also submitted that education is key to global security, therefore, there is need for change in policies in every nation of the world to cater holistically for education of every citizen which in turn could enhance tolerance, patience, love for each other, friendship and harmony in society.

In a country like Nigeria, educational administration is a necessary tool for peaceful coexistence, rapid economic growth and development. It is an essential tool in proffering solutions to the security challenges. This could be achieved according to Anyanwu (2019) through the following: strengthening the education

funding mechanism; people empowerment; curriculum diversification; creation of employment; promotion of vocational and entrepreneurship programmes and maintaining quality in education. All these, if properly harness may perhaps secure educational institutions in Niger state.

Worse of it all, prior information and threats of attacks always premeditate invasions and meet with minimal resistance. Confronted with these challenges, the fundamental questions to be asked are: How did Nigeria get to this point? Why are schools and institutions of learning soft targets of attacks? What is the responsibility of education stakeholders-policymakers, school managements and security agencies in protecting students and learning infrastructure? How and when would this menace end? Inspired by these questions, this paper explores ways that synergize between school managements and security agencies addressing insecurity relating to kidnapping, banditry and other criminal activities against students, teachers and learning institutions in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The increasing number of attacks on school facilities and its inhabitants is really disturbing in Nigeria of which Niger State tertiary institutions are part of the victims. Apart from terror and attacks, there are also cases of parents and students hiring thugs to beat lecturers and even school security personnel. This has been having negative effects on the emotional stability of both the lecturers, learners, and non-teaching personnel of various tertiary institutions in Niger state. However, much work has not been done in this regards to close this gap. Therefore, this study intends to determine the relationship between educational administration, enhanced functional education and sustainable security in tertiary institutions in Niger state, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. examine the relationship between educational administration and sustainable security
- ii. assess the impact of enhanced functional education on sustainable security
- iii. identify strategies for improving educational administration and functional education

Research Hypotheses

1. Improved educational administration practices do not lead to enhanced functional education
2. There is no significant relationship between educational administration and sustainable security.
3. Enhanced functional education does not significantly impact sustainable security.

Methodology

A correlation research design was adopted, the population of the study comprise all the administrators, lecturers and students of all tertiary institutions in Niger state. A sample of 555 respondents (administrators, lecturers and students) were selected for the study using Simple random sampling technique. Two sets of instruments tagged “Administrators/Lecturers and Enhanced Education Questionnaire (AEEQ) and Sustainable Security Questionnaire (SSQ) were used for the study.

The instruments were validated by 2 experts in the field of educational management, test and measurement who ensured the face and content validity of the instruments. The experts also validated the items in terms of clarity to ensure that all the terms that could confuse the respondents were expunged. The experts ensured that the remaining items in the instruments were true representative of the contents specified by the concepts in the study. Corrections and restructuring based on their comments, modification and recommendations were made before administration.

To ensure the reliability of the instruments, a test re-test method of reliability was used. The instruments were administered on forty (40) academic staff and four (4) Administrators in one of higher institutions in Niger, Nigeria which were not part of the sampled institutions. The instruments were administered twice within an interval of two weeks, on the same respondents and the scores obtained from the two tests were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis to determine their reliability coefficients. The reliability coefficients of 0.78 were obtained for the AEEQ and 0.85 for SSQ. These correlation coefficients were high enough for the study and hence the instruments were considered to be reliable for the study. The data were analyzed using inferential statistics. All the hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Hypothesis 1: Improved educational administration practices do not lead to enhanced functional education

In testing this hypothesis, responses to items 15-21 Section B of AEEQ, and items 1-24 Section C of the SSQ were subjected to statistical analysis involving the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result obtained is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Relationship between Educational Administration and Enhanced Functional Education

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	p-value
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Educational Administration	555	24.3600	3.2762	0.498	0.000
Enhanced Functional Education	555	90.4800	5.3150		

Table 1 showed t-cal. as 0.498. The result is significant (p-value < 0.05) and the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, improved educational administration practices lead to enhanced functional education. The relationship between educational administration practices and enhanced functional education was average and positive. This implies that correct educational leadership practices will automatically leads to enhanced functional education in Niger state tertiary institutions because this foster effective and strong leadership that can encourage support learning environment, promote lecturer development, and as well student outcomes. Also, this finding will boost quality assurance and proper resource allocation in which effective administrators can allocate resources efficiently that can help these institutions in the area of funding and as ensuring quality within the system. The result of this study corroborated the finding of Sadiq (2013) who asserted that a good administration with proper training will definitely improves the enhanced functional education. Ensuring quality and proper resource allocation in educational administration will certainly add value to functional education.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant relationship between educational administration and sustainable national security in tertiary institutions in Niger state, Nigeria.

In testing this hypothesis, responses to items 1-7 Section B of AEEQ, and items 1-24 Section C of the SSQ were subjected to statistical analysis involving the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result obtained is presented in Table 1

Table 2: Relationship between educational administration and sustainable national security in tertiary institutions

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	p-value
Educational Administration	555	24.2600	2.3496	0.481	0.000
Sustainable Security	555	90.4800	5.3150		

Table 2 showed t-cal. as 0.481. The result is significant (p-value < 0.05) and the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was a significant relationship between educational administration and sustainable national security. The relationship between educational administration and sustainable national security was average and positive.

The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between educational administration and sustainable security. This implies that educational institutions will promote social cohesion which will foster inclusivity, diversity, and tolerance, that helps to reduce conflicts and promote national stability. This corroborate the findings of Anyanwu (2019) and Omoroje (2021) that emphasis the achieving the sustainable national security through education, especially under correct educational leadership at all levels.

Hypothesis 3: Enhanced functional education does not significantly impact sustainable national security in tertiary institutions in Niger state, Nigeria.

In testing this hypothesis, responses to items 8-14 Section B of AEEQ, and items 1-24 Section C of the SNSQ were subjected to statistical analysis involving the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result obtained is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Relationship between Enhanced Functional Education and Sustainable National Security

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	p-value
Enhanced Functional Education	555	24.8500	2.9509	0.483	0.000
Sustainable Security	555	90.4800	5.3150		

Table 3 showed r-cal. as 0.483. The result is significant (p-value < 0.05) and the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, enhanced functional education significantly impact sustainable security in tertiary institution in Niger state, Nigeria. The significant impact of enhanced functional education on sustainable security was average and positive.

Going by the outcome of this finding, enhanced functional education significantly impacted sustainable national security in the area of promoting peace and stability across the higher institutions of learning, reducing illiteracy and poverty and fostering civic engagement in ensuring the sustainable security in tertiary institutions in Niger state. Functional education has sustained peace in lager percentage of the tertiary institutions which was in line with study of Olofinniyi & Adekunle (2024) who posited that education is panacea to regular unrest higher institution of learning in colleges of education in north central, Nigeria. The finding revealed that functional education will eradicate crises and unnecessary unrest in tertiary institution and as well ensure safe school environment that will be free from kidnaping, banditry activities and other criminal issues that has undermined the productivity of the institutions in Niger state, Nigeria.

Conclusion

Effective educational administration and enhanced functional education are essential for promoting sustainable security in tertiary institutions. By investing in quality education, Nigeria can reduce illiteracy and poverty, increase civic engagement, and promote national development, ultimately contributing to a more stable and secure society.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Government should invest more in education by increasing funding for education to improve infrastructure, resources, and lecturer training in order to ensure sustainable security.
2. Policy maker should promote functional education and develop curricula that focus on practical skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving to equip students for the workforce
3. Educational Administrators should foster a supportive learning environment by creating a positive and inclusive learning environment that promotes student engagement and success.
4. Administrators should collaborate with stakeholders to build partnerships with industry, government, and community organizations to promote national development and security.

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